

Basic tests of Chinese cabbage yield monitoring sensors for small-sized Korean harvesters

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Abstract

Chinese cabbage is one of the major dryland crops, especially for Kimchi, in Korea. Recently Korean government promote mechanization of the dryland crop production operations to improve the current mechanization level of 56%. The demand of precision agriculture technology has been increased for improved performance and user comfort. Objective of this study was to conduct basic tests of potential alternative sensing approaches for Chinese cabbage yield monitoring for small-sized Korean harvesters. Two approaches were investigated: mass-based sensor using load cells and volume (or area)-based sensor using a CCD camera. The mass-based sensor was installed so that the cabbages discharged from the transportation part were contacted before they fell down to the collection part. Volume-based sensor was installed on the transportation part so that the top and side images of the Cabbages were captured. Area and volume of the cabbages were obtained from the images, and then calibrated to the mass. In overall, calibration tests provided coefficients of determination of 0.97 and 0.94 for the mass-based and volume-based approaches, respectively. Effects of the distance between the sensor and cabbage were not statistically significant. Data processing to minimize the vibration and slope effects should be improved. This study showed promising results for Chinese cabbage yield monitoring, but further study should be conducted to improve the performance for different varieties and under field conditions.

Background

Recently, instead of rice, the demand for the production of crops with higher income level has been increasing in Korea, due to improved life quality, the recognition of healthy food, and changes in domestic agricultural conditions. However, development of the related agricultural machinery is insufficient and the mechanization is required. Overall mechanization rate of the dryland crops is 56.3%, and the level of harvesting operation is only 13.3%. Chinese cabbage is one of the major crops in Korea, and consumption of Chinese cabbage has been steadily increasing. It is highly necessary to develop a Chinese cabbage harvester to solve problems such as reducing and aging labor force, and reduction of cultivation area.

Yield monitoring system is one of the most important elements in precision agriculture (Pelletier and Upadhyaya, 1999). Yield monitors are the most widely used precision agriculture technology (Batte and Arnholt, 2003; Magalhaes and Cerri, 2007; Pelletier and Upadhyaya, 1999), possibly because growers perceive a high degree of benefit from the information gathering tool (Batte and Arnholt, 2003) with the data representing actual rather than surrogate measures. The growers can use the yield information and maps for management practices to improve the yield of the crop for the next season, which would increase farm profit and minimize the effects on the environment. Yield monitoring systems are commercially available for grains and other crops (Birrell et al., 1995; Thomas et al., 1999; Vansichen and Baerdemaeker, 1991), but very few yield-monitoring systems are commercially available for fruits and vegetables. The need for precision agriculture in Korea is increasing, but yield monitoring systems were developed only for rice. In this study, basic test of Chinese cabbage yield monitoring system suitable to small-sized Korean harvesters was conducted.

Methods

Figure 1 shows schematic diagram of the Chinese cabbage yield monitoring system in this study. As shown in Figure 1, the mass-based sensor was installed so that the cabbages discharged from the transportation part could be contacted before they fell down to the collection part. Additionally, volume-based sensor was installed on the transportation part and the top and side images of Chinese cabbages were captured. Area and volume of the cabbages were obtained from the images, and then calibrated to the mass. Therefore, sensor selection and experimental methods were investigated for measurement real-time yield monitoring system through basic experiments.

In this study, a load cell (OBU-10, BONGSHIN, Korea) was used to measure Chinese cabbage weight. The OBU-10 was a single-point type high-precision load cell, providing more than 1/5000 of precision. And it was possible to measure loads in various fields and high strength aluminium material. The impact plate was composed of acrylic plate with dimensions of 580 mm × 280 mm × 5 mm. The acrylic plate was attached to the four load cells with a rated output of 2 mV / V ± 10% and a capacity 10 kg. The load cell was selected because the average weight of Chinese cabbage weight was around 3 kg ~ 5 kg. A data logger (NI-USB6009, National instrument co., USA) was selected to receive the data measured by the load cell. The data logger chose the NI-USB6009 because the load cell was an analog type and compatible with LabVIEW.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the Chinese cabbage yield monitoring system

As a basic experiment to figure out adaptability, a pilot test bench of the yield monitoring system was installed to the Chinese cabbage harvester. To investigate the effect of distance between load cell and Chinese cabbage in mass-based experiments, experiments were performed using 10 Chinese cabbages of about 3 kg ~ 5 kg. The falling height of the Chinese cabbage was 10 cm to 50 cm at 10 cm intervals with a slope of the impact plate being 0°. Five replications were performed for each experiment. When weighing using a load cell, the output (mV) was calibrated for each of the distance and slope.

The volume-based system consisted of a CCD camera (VLG-12M, Baumer, Germany), a front lens, a halogen lamp, and PC with camera utility software and MATLAB. The CCD camera was installed in the basic test equipment to capture the image of the top and side of the Chinese cabbage. Using the MATLAB program, area and volume of the Chinese cabbages were calculated and then calibrated to the mass.

Figure 2. Test bench of the yield monitoring sensors for the basic tests

Results & discussion

This experiment was to judge measurement possibility of yield monitoring system using the selected sensor in the harvester. First, the actual weight of Chinese cabbage and load cell output value were compared. Figure 3 (left) shows the load cell output value by Chinese cabbage weight. When comparing the output value by Chinese cabbage weight, the linear correction equation was $Y = 0.0047X + 0.0006$ along with the coefficient of determination of R^2 (0.97). It was suggested that measurement of yield monitoring was possible using the impact plate with load cell attached from the equation and the value of R^2 . Figure 3 (right) shows the comparison of the calibrated mass and the actual weight of the Chinese cabbage as a result of the CCD camera experiment. When comparing the calibrated mass by Chinese cabbage weight, the linear correction equation was $Y = 1.03X - 0.33$ along with the high value of R^2 (0.94). It was suggested that yield monitoring can be measured by the CCD camera from the correction equation and the value of R^2 .

Tests results showed that that Chinese cabbage yield could be monitored by the load cell and the CCD camera. However, the results could be different at field conditions due to the vibration, slope, and the operation speed.

Figure 3. Comparison of the Chinese cabbage weight and sensor output using load cell (left) and CCD camera (right)

An experiment was conducted to investigate the adaptability of the sensor according to the distance between the impact plate and the Chinese cabbage. Figure 4 shows the comparison of the sensor output values when the distances between the impact plate and the Chinese cabbage were 10 cm to 50 cm at 10 cm intervals. The measured results showed the following relationships. Results showed that the distance between the load cell and the cabbage did not significantly affect the calibration equation.

$$Y = 0.05X - 0.0058, \text{ RMSE} = 0.12 \text{ (at 10 cm)}$$

$$Y = 0.05X - 0.02, \text{ RMSE} = 0.97 \text{ (at 20 cm)}$$

$$Y = 0.05X - 0.02, \text{ RMSE} = 0.13 \text{ (at 30 cm)}$$

$$Y = 0.05X - 0.0045, \text{ RMSE} = 0.13 \text{ (at 40 cm)}$$

$$Y = 0.06X - 0.02, \text{ RMSE} = 0.13 \text{ (at 50 cm)}$$

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References

- Chen B, Fu Z, Pan Y, Wang J, Zeng Z 2011. Single leaf area measurement using digital camera image. *Computer and Computing Technologies in Agriculture IV* 345: 525–530.
- Hennens D, Baert J, Broos B, Ramon H, De Baerdemaeker J 2003. Development of a flow model for the design of a momentum type beet mass flow sensor. *Biosystems Engineering* 85(4): 425–436.
- Dunn M, Billingsley J, Bell D 2006. Vision based macadamia yield assessment. *Sensor Review* 26(4): 312–317.
- Kumhála F, Kroulík M, Prošek V 2007. Development and evaluation of forage yield measure sensors in a mowing-conditioning machine. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture* 58(2): 154–163.
- Pan G, Li FM, Sun GJ 2007. Digital camera based measurement of crop cover for wheat yield prediction. *Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium. IGARSS 2007. IEEE International*. Pp. 797–800.
- Pelletier G, Upadhyaya SK 1999. Development of a tomato load/yield monitor. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture* 23(2): 103–117.
- Vellidis G, Perry CD, Durrence JS, Thomas DL, Hill RW, Kvien CK, Hamrita TK, Rains G 2001. The peanut yield monitoring system. *Transactions-American Society of Agricultural Engineers* 44(4): 775–786.
- Fravel JB, Kirk KR, Monfort WS, Thomas JS, Henderson WG, Massey HF, Chastain JP 2013. Development and testing of an impact plate yield monitor for peanuts. *ASABE Paper, Paper Number* 1620969.
- Maja JM, Ehsani R 2010. Development of a yield monitoring system for citrus mechanical harvesting machines. *Precision Agriculture* 11(5): 475–487.
- Zhou J, Cong B, Liu C 2014. Elimination of vibration noise from an impact-type grain mass flow sensor. *Precision Agriculture* 15(6): 627–638.
- Magalhães PSG, Cerri DGP 2007. Yield monitoring of sugar cane. *Biosystems Engineering* 96(1): 1–6.

Figure 4. Sensor output by distance between the impact plate and the Chinese cabbage:
(a) Distance 10 cm, (b) Distance 20 cm, (c) Distance 30 cm, (d) Distance 40 cm, (e) Distance 50 cm